

RECENT PROGRESS ON BENCHMARKING CRACKING AND DAMAGE MODELS FOR FIBRE REINFORCED POLYMER COMPOSITES

THE THIRD WORLD-WIDE FAILURE EXERCISE (WWFE-III)

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Abstract

The 3rd World-Wide Failure Exercise (WWFE-III) is an international activity aimed at assessing the maturity of well-established methodologies for the prediction various forms of damage (matrix cracking and delamination etc..) and ultimate failure of fibre reinforced polymer composite laminates. In it, selected groups, who were the originators of those methods, were provided with comprehensive input material property data and a full description of 13 challenging Test Cases (problems) to be solved and used in their analysis. These covered eight different lay-ups consisting of 0°, [0°/90°/0°], [0°/90°/0°]_s, [±45°]_s, [±50°]_s, [30°/90°/30°/90°]_s and family of [0°/45°/90°/45°]_s quasi-isotropic laminates. The loadings were: Uniaxial monotonic tension, Biaxial stresses, Loading and unloading, Bending and Thermal loading. In this paper, an up-date is given regarding the progress made by the participants for applying their models blindly, i.e. prior to receiving experimental data, to solve the specified Test Cases. A wide variety of approaches have been implemented and some of the results are described briefly.

1. Introduction

The authors have been leading international activities, known as the World-Wide Failure Exercises (WWFE), to assess the predictive capabilities of current and well established methodologies for modelling damage and failure in fibre reinforced polymer composite materials and structures. The ultimate aim is to build a strong

foundation facilitating the establishment of reliable elements/codes for virtual testing and thus quickening the life cycle of producing new designs of composite platforms. Many requirements are needed to achieve that and one of the important steps is to be able to define the accuracy, the limitations and boundaries of applicability of existing methodologies.

Three exercises have been co-ordinated:

- The First World-Wide Failure Exercise (WWFE), Ref[1], which dealt with in-plane failure criteria
- The Second World-Wide Failure Exercise, (WWFE-II), Refs[2-4], dealing with 3D failure criteria, and
- The Third World-Wide Failure Exercise (WWFE-III), addressing progressive damage under in-plane stresses, arising from in-plane, bending and thermal loadings; the effects of a stress concentration was also considered.

The first exercise was launched and coordinated between 1996-2004 to deal with benchmarking of failure criteria under two-dimensional (2-D) or in-plane loadings. A total of 15 participating groups, who were the originators of 19 different methodologies, took part and their failure theories were compared with one another and with 14 sets of experimental data. The results, in the form of papers written by the originators of the theories, have been published in three special issues of an international journal and then assembled into a textbook, Ref[1].

Two high priority gaps were identified in first exercise and those were (1) the need to examine the fidelity of failure theories when applied to three-dimensional (3-D) (i.e. triaxial) states of stress and (2) the need to assess the current status of cracking and damage models that might have the capabilities to analyse the progressive failure of materials and structures.

The Second World-Wide Failure Exercise (WWFE-II), Refs[2-4], was launched to address the first gap with the objective of extending the assessment of predictive failure criteria from 2-D to 3-D states of stress, using the same philosophy employed in the first WWFE. The organisers have successfully brought WWFE-II to completion and an up-to-date assessment of the latest lessons emerging from WWFE-II is provided in Ref[4].

In order to fill the second gap the Third World-Wide Failure Exercise (WWFE-III) is currently underway. Its goal is to benchmark and to highlight the current capabilities and the maturity of established methods for modelling various aspects of damage in composite materials. These include matrix cracks due to thermal and mechanical loads; delamination; ply constraint and stacking sequence effects; loading and unloading phenomena; failure due to stress gradients (in particular the hole size effect).

In Part A of the WWFE-III, full details are provided of the various theoretical models, which were developed and implemented by their originators. Part A serves as a platform for the participants to run their analyses and make blind predictions of a set of 13 Test Cases, which were chosen to challenge the models to their extremes. These Test Cases are listed in the table below. Thirteen different cases (Table 1) were selected covering eight different lay-ups consisting of 0° , $[0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]$, $[0^\circ/90^\circ/8/0^\circ]$, $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$, family of $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]_s$, $[\pm 45^\circ]_s$, $[\pm 50^\circ]_s$, and $[30^\circ/90^\circ/-30^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ laminates. Five different types of loadings: I -Biaxial direct stresses, II -Uniaxial monotonic tension, III-Loading and unloading, IV – Bending and V-Thermal loading. Details are provided in Ref[5].

A total of 12 groups representing 12 modelling approaches have participated, and their methods covered a wide range of failure models. The main participants are those who have developed their own failure theory/modelling capability and who have published their work widely in the open literature.

These individuals have been invited to take part and agreed to participate in a two-step process, known as 'Part A' and 'Part B' stages. Part A is devoted to making a comparison between the predictions of all the models involved and Part B is aimed at making a comparison between all the predictions and relevant experimental data, supplied by the organisers. The WWFE-III is organised to run logically through a series of activities, as follows:

Part A

- (1) Definition of the scope of WWFE-III (Selection of Test Cases and supporting data).
- (2) Identifying suitable participants and gaining their agreement to participate.
- (3) Issuing Part A data to participants.
- (4) Receipt of Part A submissions. Rigorous review process is applied for each submission.

Part B

- (5) Issuing Part B experimental data to participants.
- (6) Publication of Part A in special edition of a suitable journal.
- (7) Receipt of Part B submissions. Stringent reviewing process is adopted for each submission.
- (8) Publication of Part B in special edition of a suitable journal.

This paper gives an account of some of the lessons learnt, a comparison between the predictions of the models for all the 13 Test Cases and a set of conclusions on the similarities and the differences between the models. All the contributors' papers will be published in a special issue of Journal of Composite Materials devoted to Part A of the WWFE-III.

2. Details of methods used

A wide variety of models has been employed by the participants of the WWFE-III, Ref [17] to Ref [6]. A total of 12 methods are currently being benchmarked. The names of the participants, together with their organisations, are listed in Table 1. A brief description of these methods is made below.

1. Carrere, Laurin and Maire's model[6]

The participants provided a multiscale hybrid approach for predicting damage and failure of laminated composite structures based on the thermo-mechanical properties (stress/strain behaviour and strength) of the unidirectional plies. The approach introduces viscosity of the matrix in order to obtain an accurate description of the mesoscopic behaviour,

especially the non-linearity under shear loading. The failure criterion used is based on physical principles and introduces micromechanical aspects (such as the effect of the local debonding on the non-linear failure behaviour) at the mesoscopic scale.

The main improvements, over those proposed in the second world-wide failure exercise (WWFE II), are related to (i) the evolution and effects of the mesoscopic cracks and (ii) the coupling between those cracks and delamination (inter-ply damage). This approach has been implemented in an implicit finite element code in order to predict the strength of composite structures, exhibiting different levels of complexity (unnotched plates, open-hole plates) and subjected to complex loadings (membrane or bending loadings). The model provided solutions to all the 13 Test Cases of the WWFE-III.

2. *Chamis' model*[7]

The work is based on a relatively new commercial software that was developed by AlphaStar Corporation (USA) with the cooperation of NASA Glenn, Clarkson University, and NASA Langley. The model, referred to as General Optimization Analyzer (GENOA), uses Multi-scale (Micro-Macro) Progressive Failure Analysis (PFA), to provide theoretical predictions for damage development for the 13 Test Cases. Multiple failure criteria were utilized aimed at tackling issues related to a wide range of damage modes. The critical damage events/indexes predictions tracked trans-laminar and inter-laminar composite failures namely: matrix cracking/crack density, damage initiation/propagation delamination initiation/growth and their interaction with fiber failure.

3. *Soutis-Kashtalyan's model* [8]

The model, referred in the graphs of this paper as Kashtalyan's model, describes an analytical approach to predict the effect of intra- (matrix cracking and splitting) and inter-laminar (delamination) damage on the residual stiffness properties of the laminate which can be used in the post-initial failure analysis, taking full account of damage mode interaction. The approach is based on a two-dimensional shear lag stress analysis and the Equivalent Constraint Model (ECM) of the damaged laminate with multiple damaged plies. The application of the approach to predicting degraded stiffness properties of a multidirectional laminate with multilayer inter- and interlaminar damage is

demonstrated for cross-ply laminates made from a specific glass/epoxy system under in-plane uniaxial loading damaged by transverse and longitudinal matrix cracks and crack-induced transverse and longitudinal delamination. The model was very limited as provided predictions for only two of the Test Cases and, even for those two cases, no stress strain curves were provided. Clearly, the scope of the presented model is much less versatile than many of the others.

4. *Ladeveze's model*[9]

The model provided a detailed description of a new damage mesomodel and examined its application to solve material and structural problems for the test cases proposed in WWFE-III. The model deals with various damage scenarios and mechanisms of degradation, including diffuse intralaminar damage, diffuse interface damage, localised delamination, fibre and plasticity and can predict the evolution of a laminate's response until final failure. Some issues concerning the identification of the parameters of the mesomodel, concerning limited information, are discussed.

5. *McCartney's model* [10]

A model was used describe the development of damage in laminates, based on an energy methodology that requires knowledge of the dependence of thermoelastic constants on damage. Methods used to predict ply properties from those of the fibres and matrix are also described. Crack density in the 90 degree plies was modelled using ply refinement technique. Detailed discussion is made on a number of relevant issues (initiating defect size and shape, fibre strength, ply saturation, off-axis ply cracking, delamination, mixed mode ply cracking) and their likely effects on design.

6. *Pettermann's model* [12]

This approach described a constitutive model which considers stiffness degradation and plastic strain accumulation for the the prediction of stress strain curves and failure envelopes. The model calibration by means of the provided material data is described and the limits of applicability of the proposed constitutive model are discussed. The predictions are presented in terms of stress–strain curves and curves presenting the evolution of brittle damage and the formation of plastic strains.

7. *Pinho et al model [13]*

Pinho and his group presented predictions for the 12 of the 13 challenging Test Cases of the third World Wide Failure Exercise (WWFE-III). The constitutive model is based on plasticity theory, includes hydrostatic pressure effects and accounts for multiaxial load combination effects. The failure criteria distinguish between matrix failure, fibre kinking and fibre tensile failure. In-situ strengths are used for matrix failure. Propagation of failure takes into consideration the fracture energy associated with each failure mode and, for matrix failure, the accumulation of cracks in the plies.

8. *Sapozhnikov's model [14]*

The model presents a model, known as Generalized Daniels' Model (GDM), describing the process of micro-damage accumulation, deformation and failure of multilayered fibre reinforced composite structures under complex internal states of stress responding to external plane-stress loading. The model considers three independent types of ply micro-damage: longitudinal, transverse and shear. Nonlinear analysis, taking into account scissoring effects, is used to make theoretical predictions for all the 13 Test Cases involved in the third World Wide Failure Exercise (WWFE-III). For the prediction of notched strength of laminates with hole, the model is used with a nonlocal approach based on the specific size of ply microstructure and Neuber's hyperbola of specific deformation energy. The results are presented for all the 13 Test Cases.

9. *Soutis' model [15]*

This approach examines the application of a cohesive zone model to predict the open hole compressive (OHC) strength of an IM7/8552 carbon fibre/epoxy quasi-isotropic multidirectional laminate with an open hole and study the level-ply scaling or ply blocking effect on notch sensitivity. Cohesive zone models have been successfully applied to predict the damage from notches in engineering materials loaded in tension. They have also been used to determine the growth of fibre microbuckling from a hole in composite laminates under compression. The usual strategy is to replace the inelastic deformation associated with plasticity or microbuckling with a line-crack and to assume some form of stress-displacement bridging law across the crack faces. A plastic fibre kinking analysis and a linear reduced (softening) relationship are used for the prediction of the unnotched and open hole

compressive strength. The model was applied to solve two Test Cases only.

10. *Talreja's model [16]*

In this model, selected test cases were analysed by an approach described as synergistic damage mechanics (SDM). This approach utilizes micromechanics and continuum damage mechanics (CDM) to predict the overall mechanical response of composite laminates with ply cracking in multiple orientations. The material constants needed in the CDM formulation are calculated from stiffness property changes incurred in a reference laminate. For other laminate configurations, the stiffness changes are derived using a relative constraint parameter which is calculated from the constraint on the opening displacement of ply cracks within the given cracked laminate evaluated numerically by a finite element analysis of appropriately constructed representative unit cell. The number density of ply cracks (cracks per unit length normal to the crack planes) under quasi-static loading is calculated by an energy-based approach. Finally, the stress-strain response of a laminate is determined by combining stiffness property changes and evolution of crack number density.

11. *Varna's model [17]*

In the model, the reduction of thermo-elastic constants of laminates and their nonlinear behavior due to intralaminar cracking and nonlinear shear response of the composite are analyzed using global-local approach. The macroscopic properties of damaged laminates are expressed in simple forms containing density of intralaminar cracks and their surface displacement features obtained from local solutions. The initiation and evolution of the intralaminar damage is analyzed using strength based approach for laminates with thick layers and fracture mechanics approach for thin layers. Due to a lack of information, certain characteristics, such as statistical failure properties distribution parameters and transition point (thickness) from strength to fracture mechanics applicability, were assumed. All calculations are based on analytical expressions, some of which were developed previously through numerical analysis. The present method was applied to solve 9 out of the 13 Test Cases of the WWFE-III and that was sufficient to illustrate the capability of the damage model.

12. Vaziri- Poursartip's model[18]

The model, referred in the graphs of this paper as Vaziri's model, presented a new development of a constitutive modelling framework, referred to as COmposite DAmage Model (CODAM)), for predicting the non-linear in-plane response of composite laminates using continuum damage mechanics. The methodology is best suited for non-linear structural analysis of large scale laminated composites whose boundaries do not interfere/interact with the damage zone that develops and grows within the structure. The new development (CODAM2) addresses the deficiencies in both the numerical and material objectivity of the original version of CODAM. While the previous CODAM formulation was essentially a local smeared crack model that was augmented with crack band scaling to overcome one aspect of the numerical objectivity, namely the mesh-sensitivity, CODAM2 introduces a non-local regularization scheme to alleviate both the spurious mesh dependency and mesh orientation problems that plague all local strain-softening models. Two of 13 Test Cases, provided in the WWFE-III, which were related to the in-plane tensile and compressive loading of specimens containing open hole, were used in order to demonstrate the effectiveness of CODAM2 in predicting the damage development and the corresponding overall response in such structural loading configurations.

3. Comparison between models

In order to show typical results emanating from Part A of the WWFE-III, selected predictions have been compiled for two of Test Cases; Test Case 7 and Test Case 8. These are schematically in Figure 1. The Test Cases were selected to study the effects of lay-up sequence on the damage development and failure of a typical laminate used in aircraft.

Test Case 7

Test Case 7 deals with the prediction of the stress strain curves and crack density of $[0^\circ/-45^\circ/+45^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ quasi-isotropic laminate under uniaxial tensile along the direction of the 0° fibres. The stress strain curves predicted by the various theories are shown in Figure 2. Figure 3 shows the crack density (damage level) variations with the applied laminate strain as predicted by the various theories for the 90° and $+45^\circ$ and -45° plies. In order to show clearly the differences between the predictions of various theories, bar charts were constructed in Figure 4 to

show the failure strengths and strains of the individual theories. Furthermore, Table 3 shows the extreme predictions obtained from the models employed for the ultimate strength, strain in the loading direction, transverse strain, Poisson's ratio, crack density and initial failure strain.

Although the results in Figure 1 showed that the majority of the curves are fairly similar and linear up to failure, two theories predicted a softening behaviour at the very late stage of loading.

The following comments may be made from the data shown in the Figures 3 and 4 and Table 3:

- A small variation was observed in the ultimate strength values, which ranged from 911 to 1209 MPa. McCartney's model predicted large strength (above 1209MPa) but this was truncated arbitrarily according to maximum failure strain in the fibre direction.
- The ratio of the largest to the smallest predicted ultimate failure strains in the loading direction was 1.93 while that in the transverse direction was 2.96.
- Differences in the prediction of the crack density in the 90° plies were large. The crack density varied from 0.16 to 1.74, where the ratio between these extreme predictions reached 10.8. Note that the large crack density (1.74) was predicted by McCartney at a very large strain (not shown in the figure). The next largest damage parameter, which was equal to 1, was predicted by Sapozhnikov.
- The strain at the initiation of damage of cracking in the laminate ranged from 0.195% to 1.513% with a ratio between them equals to 7.74.
- Only three of the models predicted cracking in the 45° plies.

Test Case 8

This Test Case deals with the prediction of the stress strain curves and crack density of quasi-isotropic laminate under uniaxial tensile along the direction of the 0° fibres. However, the ply sequence is selected to be $[45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ]_s$, which is different to that in Test Case 7. The stress strain curves are shown in Figure 2. Like Test Case 7, the results of Test Case 8 show that the majority of the curves are fairly

similar and linear up to failure. Similarly, two of the theories (Chamis and Sapozhnikov) predicted a softening behaviour at the very late stage of loading.

Table 4 shows the extreme predictions obtained from the models employed for the ultimate strength, strain in the loading direction, transverse strain, Poisson's ratio, crack density and initial failure strain. The table shows the following features of the predictions:

- A small variation was observed in the ultimate strength values, which ranged from 878 to 1224 MPa, which is very close to those in Test Case 7. McCartney's model predicted large strength (above 1224MPa) but this was truncated arbitrarily according to maximum failure strain in the fibre direction.
- The ratio of the largest to the smallest predicted ultimate failure strains in the loading direction was 2.6 while that in the transverse direction was 4.6.
- Differences in the prediction of the crack density in the 90° plies were large. The crack density varied from 0.004 to 1.74, where the ratio between these extreme predictions reached 400. Varna predicted that for a specimen with 100mm gauge length, the maximum crack density value in the 90-layer corresponds to 1 crack.
- Note that the large crack density (1.74) was predicted by McCartney at a very large strain (not shown in the figure). The next largest damage parameter, which was equal to 1, was predicted by Sapozhnikov.
- The strain at the initiation of damage of cracking in the laminate ranged from 0.195% to 1.513%, giving a ratio between the largest and lowest strains to be 7.74.
- Five models predicted cracking in the 45° plies, see ref [19].

4. Concluding remarks

- The paper has provided an update of the activities and the results obtained so far as well as some of the lessons learnt from selected Test Cases. Test Cases 7 and 8 deal with the prediction of the stress strain curves and crack density of $[0^\circ/-45^\circ/+45^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ and $[45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ/-$

$45^\circ]_s$ quasi-isotropic laminate under uniaxial tensile along the direction of the 0° fibres.

- The results from Test Cases 7 and 8 have been presented in this paper where differences and similarities have been shown between the models for predicting ultimate strength, strain in the loading direction, transverse strain, Poisson's ratio, crack density and initial failure strain.
- Although small variations were observed in the final strength predictions, large differences were shown in the prediction of the initiation and the propagation of damage and cracking in the various plies.
- It is clear from the results already that the area of damage prediction remains very challenging. A lack of consensus exists in terms of how damage is developed in various laminates and how changes in geometry and lay-up sequence affect the development of cracks, delamination and ultimate failure.
- The full results of Part A of the WWFE-III are being published in a special issue of J Composite Materials and readers can find the full compilation of the predictions of all the models and their applications to providing solutions to all of the Test Cases in ref [19].

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Table (1) Details of the Test Cases used in WWFE-III.

Test Case	Laminate lay-up	Material type	Description of Required Prediction
1	[0°]	1	Shear stress strain curve with the presence of transverse tension stress of +14MPa.
2	[0°]	1	Shear stress strain curve with the presence of transverse compression stress of -34.5MPa.
3	[0°/90°/0°]	2	Stress strain curves and crack density variation
4	[0°/90 _g °/0°]	2	Stress strain curves and crack density variation
5	[0 _z °/90 _z °] _s	1	Variation of thermal expansion coefficient with crack density.
6	[0°/90°/-45°/+45°] _s	2	Stress strain curves and crack density variation
7	[0°/-45°/+45°/90°] _s	3	Stress strain curves and crack density variation
8	[45°/0°/90°/-45°] _s	3	Stress strain curves and crack density variation
9	[+30°/90°/-30°/90°] _s	2	Bending stress vs axial and transverse strains and crack density
10	[±45°] _s	2	Biaxial failure stress and strain envelopes, maximum crack density, delamination level and location.
11	[±50°] _{3s}	2	Loading and unloading curves under uniaxial loading.
12	[45°/90°/-45°/0°] _s	4	Tension strengths versus laminate hole diameter
13	[45° _m /90° _m /-45° _m /0° _m] _s	4	Tensile and compressive strengths versus laminate thickness

Table 2 A List of participants taking part in the WWFE-III.

No	Name	Organisation
1	Carrere et al[6]	ONERA (France)
2	Chamis et al[7]	NASA (USA)
3	Kashtalyan and Soutis[8]	Aberdeen Uni /Manchester Univeristy/ (UK)
4	Ladeveze and Daghia[9]	lmt.ens-cachan (France)
5	McCartney[10]	NPL (UK)
6	Pettermann et al[12]	Vienna University (Austria)
7	Pinho et al[13]	Imperial College (UK)
8	Sapozhnikov and Cheremnykh[14]	South Ural State University (Russia)
9	Soutis [15]	Manchester University (UK)
10	Talreja and Singh[16]	Texas University (USA)
11	Varna[17]	Lulea University (Sweden)
12	Vaziri and Poursartip et al[18]	University of British Columbia (UBC) (Canada)

Table 3 Extreme predictions obtained from the various theories of the strength, failure strain and crack density in Test Case 7.

	Strength MPa	Tensile strain %	Transverse strain %	Poisson's ratio	Max crack density	Initial failure strain
Maximum	1209.7	3.052	-0.337	0.330	1.743	1.513
Minimum	911.87	1.554	-0.997	0.213	0.1614	0.195
Max/Min Ratio	1.326	1.963	2.96	1.54	10.798	7.743

Table 4 Extreme predictions obtained from the various theories of the strength, failure strain and crack density in Test Case 8.

	Strength MPa	Tensile strain %	Transverse strain %	Poisson's ratio	Max crack density	Initial failure strain
Maximum	1225.08	3.87	-0.388	0.461	1.74	1.51
Minimum	878.4	1.50	-1.78	0.241	0.0043	0.195
Max/Min Ratio	1.394	2.57	4.598	1.911	400	7.743

Figure 1 Schematics of the quasi-isotropic lay-ups used in Test Case 7 (Left) and Test Case 8 (Right).

Figure 2 Comparison between the predictions of the various models for Test Case 7 (top) and Test Case 8 (bottom) used in the WWFE-III

Figure 3 Variations of the crack density with laminate strain for the $[0^\circ/-45^\circ/+45^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ carbon/epoxy laminate used in Test Case 7: Top graph for cracks in the 90° plies, middle graph for cracks in +45° plies and bottom graph for cracks in -45° plies.

Figure 4 Bar charts showing (a) failure strain in loading direction, (b) failure strain in the transverse direction, (c) failure stress and (d) maximum crack density predictions for all of the theories used in the analysis of the $[0^{\circ}/-45^{\circ}/+45^{\circ}/90^{\circ}]$, carbon/epoxy laminate used in Test Case 7.